

Novel Contextual Computing Application for attendance control on University campus through Beacons

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Resumen

Un proceso que es importante en el funcionamiento de las instituciones educativas es el control de asistencia de estudiantes y docentes. El control de presencia real en las aulas y en los horarios en los que se imparten los cursos debe ser supervisado para asegurar el normal funcionamiento en el centro académico.

Este trabajo describe una aplicación móvil contextual con características importantes para la detección de posicionamiento y control de asistencia tanto de profesores como de alumnos dentro de una universidad. El uso de la aplicación móvil reduce considerablemente la tarea de revisión periódica, que es realizada cada hora por los supervisores en las aulas de la universidad para verificar la asistencia de profesores y estudiantes. Para tener un mejor tiempo de respuesta, se diseñó y utilizó una base de datos NoSQL en lugar de la clásica base de datos relacional, esto permitirá un rápido acoplamiento a los siguientes proyectos de IoT de la universidad.

Palabras clave: *Computación Contextual, NoSQL, Internet de las Cosas, Beacons*

Abstract (150 words at most, Arial 10)

A process that is important in the operation of educational institutions is the control of attendance of students and teachers. The control of real presence in the classrooms and in the hours in which the courses are taught must be supervised to ensure normal operation from the academic center.

This work describes a contextual mobile application with important characteristics for the positioning detection and attendance control of both teachers and students within a university. The use of the mobile application reduces considerably the periodic review task, which is carried out every hour by supervisors in the university's classrooms to verify the attendance of professors and students. To have a better response time, a NoSQL database was designed and used instead of the classical Relational database, this will permit a fast coupling to the following IoT projects of the university.

Key words: *Contextual computing, NoSQL, Internet of Things, Beacons*

Introduction

A diversity of projects have been carried out to develop attendance monitoring systems(AMS), most of them focused on NFC [1], beacons -Bluetooth Low Energy(BLE)-[2-4], RFID technology[5-8], face detection[9], fingerprint[10-11], WiFi[12], ZigBee[13] among others. The cost of these systems depends on how sophisticated the system to be developed is desired and the potential integration with existing infrastructure.

A summary of the most relevant projects with NFC, RFID and Beacons(BLE) technology regarding AMS is shown in table 1, the main characteristics of the implementations are described there. Only the AMS with these technologies are shown since they are somehow competing technologies, although NFC can also be considered to be a subset of RFID technology.

The explosive growth of data due to the competitiveness in the business world demands a constant requirement for new applications and systems, these must be prepared for the already widely accepted technologies such as the internet of things(IoT), cloud computing and big data.

In the actual world, wireless networks, smartphones and tablets [14] offer great capabilities to implement contextual computing due to the large number of sensors and protocols with which they can operate. Contextual applications then provide an interface that often depends on the location, time, information received by the camera or data collected in real time [15].

Table 1 . comparison of the previous attendance systems based on RFID,BLE and NFC

Author(s)& Year	Technology	Characteristics
Jacob et al., (2015)	Mobile- NFC, Web based, XAMPP, PHP.	Introduced attendance management system for university students by using NFC mobile based attendance system. A NFC Tag ID is detected when student enters the class, the server generates a random four digit number as OTP to validate the student presence[1].
Raghav Apoorv, Puja Mathur(2016)	Beacons(Bluetooth Low Energy) and mobil technology, SQLite Database.	A Bluetooth low energy based attendance management system was built. It uses beacons given to the students which communicate with the android application of the professor smartphone[2].
Anil Kumar B G, Bhagyalakshmi K C, Lavanya K, Gowranga K H,(2016)	Beacons(Bluetooth Low Energy) and mobil technology, Relational Database Server.	A smart attendance system is presented. An Android application running in a student smartphone detect a beacon in the classroom and register the presence of the student. The student should install an app which is developed for generating automatic attendance. Once the app is installed on the android device, the student is registered with his/her unique university number and password in the server database[3].
Vinay Mahendraker, Savitha D. (2017)	BLE,GSM/GPS, Web and Mobile, MySQL,PHP.	The project consists of two different kind of thecnology; the first one being the school unit where BLE device is placed in each student ID card and readers are placed in the classroom. The second one is the bus unit where a GSM module with the GPS is placed. An Android application showing the location of the student are sent to their parents respectively[4].
Joseph Dedy Irawan, Emmalia Adriantantri, Akh Farid(2018)	RFID, microcontroller. Cloud Database.	Process of attendance is done by using RFID technology, each student has an RFID Tag which is placed near RFID Reader. The MCU receive this information and saves it in the cloud database through a Wi-Fi module[5].
Rjeib, Hasanein & Ali, Nabeel & Al Farawn, Ali & Al-Sadawi, Basheer & Alsharqi, Haider. (2018)	RFID and Arduino. Web Based.	The proposed system aims to manage student's attendance recording, provides the capabilities of tracking student absentee, support information services including students grading marks, daily timetable, lectures time and classroom numbers, and other student-related instructions provided by faculty department staff[6].
Bektassov Dias, Asif Mohammad, He Xu and Ping Tan(2020)	RFID and NodeMCU and RFID-RC522 Shield. Web Based(XAMPP,PHP,MySQL)	An RFID-based attendance management system is designed and implemented, and information service system including programmable devices and web-based applications are used[7].
Younis, Mohammed & Younis, Manal & Abed, Marwa & Alserawi, Abdulrahman. (2020).	Raspberry PI and RFID shields, Derby Database, Java.	The project proposes an automatic attendance system based on RFID, fog, and cloud computing technologies .The system protects data from wasting and ensures its arrival to the cloud even in cases of connection losing or device crashing[8].

Due to the vertiginous advances in technology, the quantity and versatility of sensors will continue to increase in the following years, this will lead to more and more mobile applications that obtain data from these sensors and generate useful contextual information to the user [16]. Contextual computing and the Internet of things are closely related, understanding the fundamentals, challenges, paradigms, architectures and trends in information technologies inside and outside of the IoT is of great interest, Jing-yi and his group [17] did a review and

classification of the context computing literature in order to create a framework that could be useful for system developers of this type.

The sensors used within IoT can be of many types, the beacons are an example of this type of sensors, they are small devices that transmit information through a protocol called BLE (Bluetooth Low Energy), they are placed strategic way indoors and carry out periodic transmissions that can be detected by intelligent equipment such as cellular phones, so they are used primarily for applications of contextual computing or indoor location, that is, they operate mainly in places where GPS systems are limited .

The infrastructure based on beacons has become very popular when implementing contextual applications , the beacons are low energy devices (they are powered by a battery whose durability is sometimes up to 5 years) that are embedded in walls, ceilings or fixed locations to serve as guides inside indoor locations; Depending on the use case, the beacons also can be carry to be used in location of people or assets . The great advantage of beacons is that through a protocol called BLE - Bluetooth Low Energy - they can communicate without major problem with mobile devices, which when connected to the internet access information related to their environment or they provide relevant information about their surroundings.

Our work focuses in the integration of beacons to develop and implement a modern contextual computing system for the control of attendance of students and professors in a university campus, in addition the same application provides a basic system of location and navigation within the main building of the university.

The era of the IoT, in which a large amount of information from sensors is channeled to databases to be stored, analyzed and processed often requires a quick response to requests for information. The growth in the number of students at the university where the present project was carried out has been exponential in recent years, and this has degraded the response time of the different services that are accessed via the web or mobile devices. All the operational systems of the university are supported by relational database(RDB) based designs. Research evaluating the performance of non-relational databases(NoSQL) versus relational ones show that for IoT-type projects, No-SQL databases are more convenient[18-20].

In order to obtain an acceptable response time and thinking about the diversity of projects related to IoT that the university has planned in the near future, the AMS project was designed using a NoSQL Database, which will be synchronized with information from the institutional database[21-22], therefore the main contribution of the project is the use of an alternative that allows a sustainable growth of the technological needs of the academic institution, besides the integration of university buildings navigation maps in the app developed.

The reminder of this paper is structured as follows. In section two, we reviewed the fundamentals of BLE and the hardware and software utilized in the project. Section three describes the methodology used in the development process, our architecture design of the NoSQL database and the general design of the application. Section four shows the interfaces of the application and describes the experimental results obtained. Section five gives the conclusions and the future work we are working on.

BLE Protocol, Hardware and Software used

Bluetooth Low Energy Protocol (BLE)

The beacons are devices that implement the BLE protocol, the specification of this protocol was developed by the Bluetooth Special Interest Group (Bluetooth SIG), from the Bluetooth 4.0 version are supported communications that do not require establishing connections or being transmitting / receiving a continuous flow of data. The BLE protocol is mostly focused on sporadic communications over time, not a continuous flow of data between two entities such as classic Bluetooth, this makes a small power consumption of this devices. Indoor positioning systems (IPS) and real-time location systems (RTLs) have been proposed by authors [23-25] using technology based on these fundamentals. The beacons are programmed to periodically transmit a coded "advertisement" signal of a few bytes at intervals of the order of a few seconds, through other devices with higher energy consumption this signal is received and through geometric techniques or similar the location of people is estimated, this based on the intensity of the transmitted signal power (RSSI), arrival / departure angle (AoA and AoD) or time of Arrival (ToD). It is worth mentioning that the BLE protocol is not compatible with classic Bluetooth, so Bluetooth SIG defines images in the product logos indicating Bluetooth, Bluetooth Smart or Bluetooth Smart Ready, the firsts support the classic version, the seconds for BLE devices and the third ones for devices that

support both protocols. Bluetooth speakers, beacons and smartphones are common examples of each of the electronic components with these specs.

BLE technology operates in the 2.4GHz spectrum range just like classic Bluetooth technology, but uses a different set of channels. Instead of 79 channels of 1 MHz of traditional Bluetooth, BLE has 40 channels of 2 MHz. There are 3 advertisement channels – 37,38 and 39 - that do not interfere with WiFi communication typically configured at access points, so that in traditional applications of IPS, RTLS or contextual computing that do not require an explicit connection and exchange of information, non-interference with that network is guaranteed -see Figure 1-.

Figure 1. Frequency map of the BLE protocol

There is enough literature to understand the basics of the BLE protocol [26-29], the protocol is very versatile and it is certainly a base in the communication of devices on the Internet of things. Substantial improvements in the BLE standard are given in the last two specifications, in version 5.0 the transmission speed reaches up to 2Mbps compared to 1Mbps in its initial version, in addition to quadrupling the scope with respect to the previous version - this means a distance of up to 500 meters according to information of certain commercial Bluetooth modules -.

Beacons

The next beacons were used in our experimentation:

Estimote brand beacons were used to place them in strategic parts of a university building for the experimentation. Beacons with the following characteristics were programmed through the web application and an application of the company Estimote Inc.:

Transmission Power: 4mW, Advertisement interval: 300ms, Transmission Package: Eddystone UID.

Kontakt brand card beacons were used to be carried by some teachers and students. The beacons were configured through the manufacturer's website with the following configuration:

Transmission power: -65dbm (power in dB at 1-meter distance), Advertisement interval: 1000ms, Transmission Package: Eddystone UID.

Software

The main software used in the project is detailed below:

Android Studio

This platform is used to develop application for the Android operating system It is consider to be an ideal tool to make simple and sophisticated applications. It provides an excellent visualization modules for the elaboration of screens, besides allowing the creation of components in a simple way. On this platform was developed all the software that generates the interaction between the beacons, the mobile device and the database in the cloud.

Google Firebase

Firebase is the new mobile development platform that allows to develop cross-platform applications (Android, iOS and web) through a non-relational database. It allows you to access a web service and have the application working with data in the cloud. Something important to note, is that unlike the multiple technologies that appear day by day, this tool has considerably extensive documentation to develop through it.

In the majority of mobile applications the greatest processing load is carried out in the interaction with the device; in order to have a quick response it was decided to use a non-relational or documentary database (commonly called NoSQL database), the documentary databases are capable of being much faster than relational [19-20], since they do not require searching and extracting information found in several tables linked together.

Due to the future growth of the IoT projects in the university, the developed application was planned and implemented using a NoSQL database, this provides freedom and flexibility in its potential evolution, the goal to

connect in a near future with new applications of IoT and cloud technology will be achieved easily. In a few weeks there will be also a project focused on synchronizing the relational and NoSQL databases[21-22] to integrate operational and IoT systems.

Methodology

The stages of the methodology used for the development of the system documented in this article were:

a) Development of site maps to evaluate

Because the experimental installation did not have an updated plan, an architectural survey of the main university building was carried out with AutoCAD software. The building consists of eight levels, for the purpose of this experimentation the plans of three of the different levels were developed, in these are the mainly classrooms of the different university careers offered by the institution.

b) Installation of beacons based on BLE technology

Nine beacons (Bluetooth Low Energy transmitters) of the Estimote brand were programmed transmitting at a power of 4dBm and installed in classroom areas at different levels of the university building, the ID was registered - which is similar to the Ethernet address of a network card - of each beacon in a database in the cloud, so that the application could automatically recognize at what level and in what area of rooms the detected beacon was located.

c) Cloud database feed

The map information of the different levels of the main building, classrooms, schedules, teachers, groups and student lists was uploaded to Google's NoSQL Firebase database; This was done manually through the interface that provides the same database. There was the option to import the information from the official database of the university, but due to security and time restrictions, it was decided to enter the information directly.

A simplified scheme of the organization of the database is shown in Figure 2, it reveals three main sets: Classrooms, Beacons and Groups, within each set is filled with information and segments that in turn contain more information and subgroups referring to the main entity, for example, we have different classrooms that contain schedules per day which in turn contain classes for each hour, all this integrated into a design similar to the philosophy of object programming.

Figure 2. Scheme of the NoSQL database used

d) Application development to connect to the beacons and the cloud database

Using the Android development environment and the BLE libraries, an application was implemented in order to detect the beacons placed inside the main university building, this in order to provide contextual information regarding each different environment, providing information of a map of the area, location of access to upper and lower levels, classrooms, schedules, teachers, groups and lists of students within the classrooms at the time of use of the application. A pictorial scheme of the infrastructure used and the general operating mechanism of the developed application is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. App general operating mechanism

The internal operation of the application is divided into two processes fundamentally: the first one is the interaction between the user and the mobile device interface, the other is the search for beacons in the environment, this is carried out through the background execution of a known beacons tracking algorithm, identification is done through its media access address. In a typical application, the beacons continuously transmit each time interval defined in them - they can be programmed in intervals of milliseconds to several seconds -; Once a beacon is identified, a process is started by accessing the database to obtain the set of classrooms that surround it, all interactions with the database are asynchronously, any changes that occur in it will be reflected in instant way in the application. Once the classroom is chosen in the interface, a chain is created with the address where the information segment that we are going to access is located, a similar process also occurs when obtaining the list of students of the chosen classroom.

Experimental Results

The contextual application developed will support the work of educational assistants, staff and students of the Northeast University located in Tampico, Tamaulipas, Mexico. The university has a complex architectural distribution, with buildings of up to eight levels and it is easy to get lost within them; The job of the mobile application is to give a guide to the user through a basic navigation system that indicates a map of the site where it is located, the different accesses to it to the lower and upper level and the courses that are taken in the different classrooms in the area at that time along with the classroom schedule throughout the week. Figure 4 shows the survey of the third level of the building where the experimentation was carried out and the location of the beacons for this level.

Figure 4. Architecture of the third level Northeast University

According to the beacon received by the mobile device, a list of rooms that are located in that area along with the map of the area and the access to the upper and lower level of the building appears in the interface, in figure 5 the interface shown to the user appears for one section of the third level of the main building.

Figure 5. User Interface

The educational assistant is an employee of the university who continuously walks the classrooms and buildings verifying the attendance of professors. The application is useful for him, since when making the selection of a classroom, the system shows the list of schedule-courses in that room during the week, the teacher who should be teaching the class there, the photograph of the teacher, the name of the course and also has access to the list of students who should be taking that class. All information is downloaded through the cellular phone from the cloud using the Google Firebase database. Figure 6a shows the interface that is presented when selecting a specific classroom. When manually scrolling over the top of the interface, the image of the schedule is exchanged during the week to a map implemented with an animated GIF that indicates the area where it is located and the possible exit routes to the lower and upper levels of the building.

Figure 6. (a)Educational supervisor interface, (b)List of assistance implemented through card type beacons

Card-type beacons Kontakt brand and similar in size to a credit card were purchased and programmed, the factory-calibrated power on these beacons is -65dB at one meter distance and with an advertisement period of 1 second ;These beacons were assigned to some teachers and students and this information was registered in a cloud database.

The application was then modified to place a mark on the interface when it detected the presence of the teacher as shown in figure 6a. Figure 6b shows a list of students where an X mark appears to those students who were not given beacons, meaning in some way that they were absent according to how the application was programmed; this is fully functional in the case that all students had their own beacon as identification. At the moment when the beacons decrease their price (currently the price is between \$ 35 and \$ 45 dollars for the brands used) this type of identification could be very useful for a university system that look for a semi-automatic control of teachers and students, with this, the teacher avoids the administrative task of passing the list, the educational assistant would then do this work when passing in front of the classroom and all the information in these records would be available in the cloud.

Conclusions and future work

Satisfactory results were obtained in all tests performed with beacons focused on contextual computing applications with mobile devices. The potential for this type of technology is unlimited, in the case of use presented all the information is in the cloud and the functionality of immediately sending messages or emails to parents, career directors, etc. could be added relatively easily, concerning to absences of teachers and students. Certainly, the application is not a 100% reliable solution in terms of attendance because a student and a teacher could be in the immediate vicinity and be detected by the application thus registering their attendance, or a student could give his beacon to another student who did show up for classes and this would have his attendance recorded. The arrival of more sophisticated technology such as the Bluetooth 5.1 specification released in 2019, which has directional detection could solve any of the aforementioned problems, but it will be a few months before this technology appears fully functional in the products that are compatible with the specification.

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